

Optimization of molecular weight distribution in terpolymer DUV Photoresists.

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Polymeric photoresists have drawn considerable attention during the last many decades. Photoresist technology as a step in the microlithography process can help to create faster and smaller devices. In the area of polymer materials, ter-polymerization is one of the most important means to improve the properties of existing polymer and to develop new polymers. The end-use properties of polymers are largely dependent on their molecular weight distribution. Molecular weight distribution is an essential parameter to obtain polymers with desired properties. Recently, studies on molecular weight distribution have been the focus of increasing attention, A change in the molecular weight leads to changing in fundamental properties of photoresist. Herein, we demonstrate the simple procedure for optimization of molecular weight distribution of a terpolymer DUV photoresist by changing the concentration of AIBN in a polymeric solution without using additional inhibitors. Traditional photoresist using 248 nm UV wave length resolve features between 0.25-0.18 μ m.

A terpolymer was synthesized by polymerization of 4-hydroxystyrene, styrene, and t-butyl acrylate with different concentrations of AIBN.

Fig: Lithography pattern of polymer

Keywords : DUV Resists, molecular weight , optimization.

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